

UDC 338.48 EDN: QUUVTW
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15576108

Sandra ZEPEDA-HERNÁNDEZ

University of Guadalajara (Guadalajara, State of Jalisco, Mexico)
Professor and Researcher; e-mail: sandra.zepeda@academicos.udg.mx

Fabiola Cristina COSTA DE CARVALHO

University Panamerican Center of High Estudios, Unicepes (Zitácuaro, State of Michoacán, Mexico)
Professor and Researcher; e-mail: fabiola.cvho@gmail.com

TOURISM IN THE PUERTO VALLARTA METROPOLITAN AREA, MEXICO: CHALLENGES AND OPPORTUNITIES FOR THE XXI CENTURY

Abstract. Internationally, sun and beach tourism continue to be the main marketable product for destinations around the world, such as the case of the Puerto Vallarta Metropolitan Area in Jalisco State, Mexico. This article aims to reflect on mass tourism's impact on the region, with a perspective on the first half of the 21st century within the framework of sustainable tourism. The research approach involves qualitative methods such as participant observation, in-depth interviews, and documentary research based on consulting official government sources, data banks, and newspaper analysis. The discussion focuses on the problems associated with the political-administrative aspects of geographical connotation, the challenge of diversifying tourism products with an emphasis on attention to specific growing niches, as well as the ordering of unregulated accommodation and priority attention to social justice to the host population. As a result, the integral planning of the tourist destination is identified as a fundamental issue on which a new stage can be built for the region for the benefit of the resident population, in addition to the diversification of the tourism product considering the micro-regions and its potential within the framework of sustainability.

Keywords: Tourism, Sustainability, Tourism Planning, Puerto Vallarta, Bahía de Banderas

Citation: Zepeda-Hernández, S., & Costa de Carvalho, F. C. (2024). Tourism in the Puerto Vallarta Metropolitan Area, Mexico: Challenges and Opportunities for the XXI Century. *Sovremennye problemy servisa i turizma [Service and Tourism: Current Challenges]*, 18(4), 132–150. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.15576108.

Article History

Received 1 August 2024
Accepted 20 November 2024

Disclosure statement

No potential conflict of interest was reported by the author(s).

© 2024 the Author(s)

This work is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY-SA 4.0). To view a copy of this license, visit <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/>

УДК 338.48 EDN: QUUVTV
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15576108

СЕПЕДА-ЭРНАНДЕС Сандра

*Университет Гвадалахары (Гвадалахара, шт. Халиско, Мексика)
профессор и исследователь; e-mail: sandra.zepeda@academicos.udg.mx*

КОСТА ДЕ КАРВАЛЬЮ Фабиола Кристина

*Университетский Панамериканский центр передовых исследований, Unicespes
(Ситакуаро, шт. Мичоакан, Мексика);
профессор, научный сотрудник; e-mail: fabiola.cvlho@gmail.com*

ТУРИЗМ В АГЛОМЕРАЦИИ ПУЭРТО-ВАЛЬЯРТА, МЕКСИКА: ВЫЗОВЫ И ВОЗМОЖНОСТИ ДЛЯ XXI ВЕКА

«Туризм солнца и пляжа» по-прежнему остаётся одним из самых прибыльных направлений в мировом туризме, обеспечивающий доход для множества регионов, включая агломерацию Пуэрто-Вальярта в штате Халиско, Мексика. Данная статья посвящена исследованию влияния массового туризма на этот регион с точки зрения принципов устойчивого развития и охватывает период первой половины XXI века. В рамках исследования применялись качественные методы: наблюдение за участниками туристической деятельности, углублённые интервью и анализ документальных источников, включая консультации с официальными государственными структурами, статистическими данными и публикациями в прессе. Обсуждение фокусируется на ключевых проблемах, связанных с политико-административным восприятием региона, необходимостью диверсификации туристических предложений с акцентом на перспективные ниши, регулированием нелегального размещения и обеспечением социальной справедливости для местного населения. В результате исследования выявлена фундаментальная необходимость в комплексном планировании туристического направления, которое позволит заложить основу для нового этапа развития региона, ориентированного на благополучие местных жителей и диверсификацию туристической продукции с учётом потенциала отдельных микрорайонов и принципов устойчивого развития.

Ключевые слова: туризм, устойчивость, планирование туризма, Пуэрто-Вальярта, залив Бандерас

Для цитирования: Сепеда-Эрнандес С., Коста де Карвалью Ф.К. Туризм в агломерации Пуэрто-Вальярта, Мексика: вызовы и возможности для XXI века // Современные проблемы сервиса и туризма. 2024. Т.18. №4. С. 132–150. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15576108.

Дата поступления в редакцию: 1 августа 2024 г.
Дата утверждения в печать: 20 ноября 2024 г.

1. Introduction

The health crisis caused by COVID-19 marked a milestone in contemporary history that drastically impacted the world's tourist destinations. Thus, they were paralyzed, and the way was opened for a media discussion on the "new reality" and the recovery of the tourist markets within the framework of more responsible tourism.

Social distancing and the new paradigm of care – health and environment – have generated a broader vision of the possibilities of remaining competitive in post-pandemic times. However, this recuperation of global tourism to pre-pandemic levels is not expected before 2024, according to UNWTO (2023), mainly because of challenges in the economy, such as the high inflation and interest rates, as well as the spike in oil and food prices.

Otherwise, all the possibilities for innovations, new markets, and repositioning of the market put into discussion, the tourism system demand and offer dynamic maintained, and sun and beach tourism continues to be the main marketable product in the world. In the case of Mexico, it is the most important segment, being the region of Quintana Roo, on the Caribbean coast, the one with the most international arrivals (43,9% in January 2023¹).

On the Pacific coast of Mexico, tourism is also an essential activity in many places. In such territory, Puerto Vallarta city is located in one of the largest and most beautiful bays, due to its peculiar geographical characteristics. It integrates the Interstate Metropolitan Area of Puerto Vallarta-Bahía de Banderas (AMIPV-BB, in Spanish acronymous), formed by two municipalities, Puerto Vallarta, which belongs to the state of Jalisco, and Bahía de Banderas, as part of the state of Nayarit. In 2020, the AMIPV-BB concentrated 479,471 inhabitants, of which 49.8% are women and 50.2% are men.

The origin of tourist activity in the region is not homogeneous and it rather responds to various stages of the public and political life of each municipality. This aspect is relegated to the enormous challenges currently facing the region as a whole, in reaching a point of no return, in which planning the territory in a more orderly manner and considering a balance between the various dimensions and actors involved, has become a priority issue.

In that order of ideas, this article addresses the challenges and opportunities facing the tourist region of the Puerto Vallarta-Bahía de Banderas Interstate Metropolitan Area, especially analyzing the integrated planning challenges (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1 – Puerto Vallarta Metropolitan Area

Source: Government of Jalisco, 2019

In the article, the theoretical perspective discusses the construction of territory and tourism planning. Then the methodological aspects that gave rise to the findings are presented, as well as the subsequent discussion. Thus, the integral planning of the tourist destination is considered the cornerstone on which a new stage can be built for the region, in which it is considered as one, beyond the political-administrative divisions, the metropolitanization of the area, for the benefit of the resident population. The tourist product is diversified considering the various micro-regions that comprise it and its potential within the framework of sustainability.

¹ Datur-Sectur (2023). *Llegada de Visitantes Extranjeros Vía Aérea por Aeropuerto a abril 2023*. URL: <https://datatur.sectur.gob.mx/SitePages/Visitantes%20por%20Nacionalidad.aspx>, in 16th June, 2023.

Territory and Tourism Planning

Tourism is based on the social valuation of certain geophysical and geo-cultural components (resources-attraction factors) that constitutes a specific type of leisure and implies displacement from the usual place of residence (Vera et al., 2013). The World Tourism Organization would add to this definition that the reasons for travel do not include only leisure motivations, but also business, among others. Tourism, as a contemporary social phenomenon with a complex structure, implies the operation of the territory and the creation of urban and regional structures. As to serving as an organizing factor, it becomes a mechanism for capital accumulation (Cordero, 2006; Vera et al., 2013) and an instrument for the private appropriation of wealth (Bifano-Oliveira & Pimentel, 2022). In this sense, tourism also constitutes "a tool for the extraction of surplus value from work and a technique to capture income from singular physical and cultural resources" (Vera et al., 2013: 200).

There is no doubt that to reach economic, social, and environmental improvement of a tourism destination, the planning process and its implementation and monitoring must be integrated into those broader planning processes (Dos Anjos, Henz & Calçada, 2009). This complexity constitutes an undeniable transcendence of planning the territory for tourism purposes, and the organization or lack of it in both coastal and inland spaces will be reflected in the construction of the social reality of each tourist destination. Consequently, two types of tourism intervention in the organization of space are identified: planned and spontaneous (Vera et al., 2013).

More specifically, considering the Latin-American scenario strategic planning, in the local context, continues to be the most used instrument of planning in the public sector from the 1980s to the 2010s (Azcué Vigil, 2018). In this sense tourism planned destinations should have legal instruments and land use regulations that define the general and organic structure of the territory (Santos, 1999).

According to Vera et al. (2013: 202), those "respond to an initial approach of quantitative and qualitative objective in the medium and long term, to provide the tourist space with services and equipment [...] have an orderly tourism development, clear and follows a pre-established plan".

On another scale of intervention, there is the logic of "spontaneity", which implies the territorial insertion of tourism with strong processes of economic growth but with notorious social and environmental problems, where the role of certain key actors, such as local leaders, play a decisive role in terms of promoting or regulating the tourist process. Meanwhile, portions of planned territory can be observed together with real estate-tourist developments, carried out outside of any control, which implies the indiscriminate privatization of land and resources, as well as the degradation of the territorial structure and of the landscape itself, that has supported tourism development (Vera et al., 2013). Hence, spontaneity is translated into heterogeneous, unfinished, and composite landscapes, which can be characterized in terms of spatial confusion (Dewailly, 2006).

On the other hand, regarding the spatial, social, and economic relationship of tourism development, integrated or segregated tourist spaces are identified, as well as the main difference which lies in the effects they produce on the local economy and society. Thus, other elements have started to play an important role in the tourism organization of the territories, apart from the rationality of the planning documents, that is the negotiation among diverse agents that take part in the tourism system (Velasco, 2016).

According to systemic theory, it is supposed that in the integrated tourist spaces, a more harmonious and integral tourist development is generated, resulting in the acceptance and identification of the local population with the project that is promoted. By contrast, segregated tourist spaces are characterized by a spatial, social, and economic disconnection from the environment and have few effects on the local economy and

society, fostering social unrest among the local population as it allows for the appreciation of differences and contrasts (Vera et al., 2013; Bifano-Oliveira & Pimentel, 2022).

Likewise, segregated spaces are mainly controlled by large multinational tourism marketing companies and require large public and private investments; additionally, local communities are ignored, although at the same time, this system generates important sources of employment as a result of the large investments implemented in the territory (Cordero, 2000). Thus, a strong contradiction is evident in the face of a "marked territoriality", marked by natural beauty and a weak social and civil citizenship characterized by poverty and a lack of compliance with basic rights, since the benefits that the receiving community receives from the Tourism, in general, is scarce compared to the proportion of income that tourism generates, which accentuates the contradiction between tourist territoriality and local citizenship (Cordero, 2006).

Additionally, destinations with segregated spaces have economic, urban, social, and environmental effects that threaten coastal areas with an accelerated transformation of land use and the consequent environmental cost, since "hotels, ports, real estate developments, golf courses, among others, replace wetland, mangrove, dune, and beach areas" (Vera et al., 2013:201).

For Enríquez (2008), the consequence of a segregated tourist development generates high real estate speculation and substantially increases the value of the land -contributing significantly to the inflationary effect of the region-, it also increases the growing demand for housing for newly employed immigrant residents. Some examples are in the construction industry and tourist services, spaces for illegal occupation proliferating on the periphery, as well as an increase in demand for public services and urban infrastructure and equipment.

Sustainable Development and Tourism

The notion of "Development" emerged from economic theories, which soon became an analytical category under the domain of

economic sciences, adding adjectives throughout the 20th century according to the field of study. The concept of Development thus began to incorporate other concerns not only about growth but also about "Well-being" as an analytical category, which was accompanied by proposals for indicators such as the Human Development Index (HDI) and the Gini Coefficient, both widely accepted by the international academic community.

In this context, by the end of the 1980s, concerns about the balanced development of tourism and the quality of tourism activity through the conservation of natural resources in tourist destinations arose, and the concept of "sustainable tourism" emerged opposing the concept of "mass tourism" (Zepeda & Costa, 2017). During this period, the debate about the destructive impacts of massive and disorderly tourism increased due to a lack of planning, resulting in few social and economic benefits for the receiving society, in addition to producing negative impacts on the environment (Cavalcanti, 2006).

At the end of the last millennium, the debate on what "should be" opened up strongly and placed a more balanced development between society and nature at the center. "Sustainable development" emerges as a basis that gives rise to international commitments such as the Millennium Development Goals and, later, the Sustainable Development Goals of the United Nations Organization.

Moreover, maintaining the attractiveness of environmental resources (Durić & Topler, 2023) as well as promoting ethical practices in the tourism business (Zepeda, Costa & Ortega, 2023), has become the basis of tourism discussion. Both planning axes are based on the World Tourism Organization (UNWTO) definition of sustainable tourism, as that which meets the needs of tourists at the same time as the needs of the destination itself, while protecting and expanding opportunities for the future by valuing national culture (López & Godoy, 2014). Consequently, UNWTO member countries are advised to integrate "sustainability" as part of their political agendas until the year 2030, to concretize the

sustainable tourism agenda (Zepeda & Costa, 2017).

Among the advantages and contributions of the generation of structured knowledge to the planning and management of tourism in its evolution towards sustainability are the improvement in decision-making, timely detection of problems, and implementation of corrective and preventive measures, as well as the evaluation of results (UNWTO, 2005).

In specific terms, the apprehension of sustainable tourism actions has been discussed around the construction of indicators as a potential means of identifying and evaluating the results of actions and allowing the measurement of changes for the development of tourism management, this is "allowing changes in the tourism structure and its internal factors, as well as changes in external factors that affect tourism and the repercussions of tourism" (Vera et al., 2013: 378), such indicators provide the signals, regulations, and data for designing policies or observing them or government decisions (Sancho & García, 2006).

Vera et al. (2013), propose a framework composed of indicators that could deal with natural resources, the environment, the economy, or the conservation of cultural heritage, as well as social values and organizational issues. In this way, the indicators are structured from four areas or subsystems: environmental, sociocultural, economic, and

political-institutional. The present work analyzes precisely these four dimensions to characterize and analyze the main elements that distinguish the tourism management of the AMIPV-BB.

2. Methods

This article responds to a descriptive investigation that aims to evaluate and analyze the management of the Puerto Vallarta Metropolitan Area (AMIPV-BB) as a tourist destination within the framework of sustainability. For the above, qualitative techniques were used, particularly documentary research that allows identifying the social tourism phenomenon of the study area in the present and near past. In particular, primary and secondary sources of information were consulted, and more specifically, databases, official government sources, as well as documents of interest for research such as newspapers, magazines, reports of tourism in the study locus, and various academic articles were collected and selected.

The information was organized according to the four areas in which the sustainable tourism indicators are structured: 1) Environmental, 2) Socio-cultural, 3) Economic, and 4) Political-Institutional (Vera et al, 2013). Derived from the exploratory nature of the study, one to two aspects have been initially considered for each dimension.

By the foregoing, the information is analyzed according to the aspects described in the following table 1.

Table 1 – Dimensions of analysis

<i>Environmental</i>	<i>Socio-cultural</i>	<i>Economic</i>	<i>Political-Institutional</i>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Environmental indicators and environmental protection actions • Transformation of uses and degradation of soil and landscape 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Conservation of cultural heritage • Social well-being and perceived quality of life 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Occupancy percentage (lodging) • Profile and Satisfaction of the tourist 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Territorial planning instruments

Source: Authors.

Additionally, participant observation and in-depth interviews with key actors of the communities that comprise the Metropolitan Area under study were carried out from January to April 2022.

3. Results

3.1. Environmental dimension

Environmental impacts can be divided into direct and indirect, depending on whether they are a direct consequence of

tourist activity, such as real estate construction and soil modification; or, indirect, such as the generation of urban infrastructure necessary for the population: communication routes, highways, and services, among others. In any case, environmental impacts are the result of uncontrolled development, given the omission of a social commitment and a system dominated by economic speculation (César & Arnaiz, 2006).

a. Environmental indicators and environmental protection actions

According to official data, some environmental indicators consider reforestation and complaints received at the local and federal levels. The complaints in both municipalities of the AMIPV-BB in recent years are shown below.

Table 2 – Environmental indicators, Bahía de Banderas municipality 1995–2016

	<i>Trees planted</i>	<i>Reforested area, ha</i>	<i>Complaints received in environmental matters</i>
1995	97,595	133	1
2000	21,796	20	10
2005	11,000	10	75
2010	0	0	47
2012	8,000	13	62
2014	NA	NA	99
2016	NA	NA	98

Source: Own elaboration based on INEGI, 2015, 2017

According to Table 2, the debacle in the reforested area and the number of trees planted in Bahía de Banderas is observable, going from 97,595 in 1995 to only 8,000 in 2010. Of equal importance, the number of complaints received in environmental matters is increased exponentially from 1 complaint in 1995 to 98 in 2016.

According to a 2017 report, in Puerto Vallarta the number of complaints in environmental matters reaches 29 cases, very high for the state of Jalisco, being only below Zapopan and Guadalajara (INEGI, 2017).

The complaints are concentrated on the rational use of territorial space and its natural resources, associated with land use. The other reiterated aspect in the complaints is related to the invasion of areas of traversable mainland and adjacent to the beach, associated with the repeated public complaints of their appropriation by private parties (Table 3).

Table 3 – Complaints topics received in environmental matters, Puerto Vallarta, 2016

<i>Ambit</i>	<i>No. of complaints</i>
Atmosphere	0
Land use	0
Wild flora	0
Wildlife	5
Forest	5
Protected marine species	1
Ecological Planning and environmental impact	8
Federal Maritime Land Zone	8
Other	2
Total	29

Source: INEGI, 2017

Thus, the number of complaints for environmental crimes in the Metropolitan Area for 2017 reached 127 complaints for that year alone. A figure well above the parameters for any municipality in Jalisco or Nayarit.

Likewise, it is estimated that in Puerto Vallarta only 61.5% of the population in private homes eliminate their waste by delivering it to the public collection service and 37.5% throw it into the dump, a very low number compared to the majority of municipalities in Jalisco (INEGI, 2017). By opposition, Puerto Vallarta has 7 public wastewater treatment plants, the same number as some municipalities in the Guadalajara Metropolitan Area with more than half a million inhabitants².

On the other hand, the Metropolitan Zone has three protected natural areas: the *Cuenca Alimentadora del Distrito de Riego 043* located in both municipalities; the Marietas Islands, temporarily closed in 2016 in an attempt to preserve the natural heritage³; and

² San Pedro Tlaquepaque with 687,127 inhabitants has 7 public treatment plants, and Tlajomulco de Zúñiga has 8 plants for its 601,122 inhabitants (INEGI, 2020).

the *Estero el Salado* in Puerto Vallarta, a municipal ecological conservation zone that integrates 169 ha (IIEG, 2020). *El Salado* is considered the main public green space of the city and, according to public reports, it is threatened by the spill of sewage from the central-north collector of the water utility (Seapal), as well as by urban growth and, recently, due to the waste of face masks that put the fauna of the natural area at risk, as there is the possibility of their ingestion and death (Frías, 2019; 2021).

In recent years, efforts have been made to declare the *El Quelele* Lagoon and its mangrove area as a protected area in Bahía de Banderas, however, real estate pressure is present and the construction of housing developments has been allowed, offering those "unique ecological habitats in the Bay of Banderas" (Zepeda, 2021:163).

Furthermore, the AMIPV-BB has 18 certified beaches⁴ that imply compliance with environmental education, water quality, environmental management, and safety criteria. The certifications are shown in Table 4.

Table 4 – Beaches certified in the AMIPV-BB, 2020

<i>Certification Type</i>	<i>Blue Flag (International)</i>	<i>Clean Beach (NMX-AA-120)</i>
<i>Puerto Vallarta</i>	2	9
<i>Bahía de Banderas</i>	3	5
<i>AMIPV-BB</i>	5	14

Source: Own elaboration based on IIEG, 2020.

b. The transformation of uses and degradation of soils and landscape

The rise of tourism in the AMIPV-BB has brought with it a wave of migration from various parts of the country, among which the central and southern areas stand out, derived from the economic dynamism of tourism and

its capacity for job creation. The demographic growth of the AMIPV-BB reaches 479,471 inhabitants in 2020 (INEGI, 2020). The drastic population growth from the nineties substantially increased the demand for housing, which is evident in the extension of the urban sprawl towards the remaining rural area of the municipality, as it has the ideal geographical characteristics for real estate.

The growth in the number of real estate developments is one of the main factors that affect the transformation and use of land. Urban growth is oriented towards the flat area, since the natural limitations of the mountain formations have led to accelerated growth of real estate developments, initially in the towns in the interior of Bahía de Banderas and, more recently, the area of *Las Juntas-El Zancudo*, a rural landscape corridor of approximately 14 kilometers that circumscribes human settlements on the sides of state highway 544 that leads to the foot of the western highlands in the state of Jalisco.

Table 5 – Population growth in San Clemente de Lima and San Vicente, 1990–2020

<i>Year / Location</i>	<i>San Clemente de Lima</i>	<i>San Vicente</i>
1990	53	2873
1995	90	3543
2000	125	5776
2005	172	7849
2010	1021	14 324
2020	9565	38 666

Source: INEGI, Census 1990-2020

The growth in the number of localities makes it possible to identify the growth in demand for housing. In the towns of the interior of Bahía de Banderas, a phenomenon of real estate explosion was gestated and developed that is evident in the population growth from the nineties. As an example, table 5 shows the

³ The Islas Marietas National Park was temporarily closed in May 2016 by the National Commission for Protected Areas (CONANP) to implement a Rescue Plan derived from its importance as a Ramsar site of international scope, as well as a Serial World Heritage Site of the Gulf Islands of California, UNESCO (2004) and Reserve of the Biosphere of UNESCO (2008).

⁴ The Nuevo Vallarta beach in Bahía de Banderas has both certifications, so this number may not match the sum of certified beaches in Table 4.

population growth in the town of *San Clemente de Lima*, where one of the lowest living standards in the Metropolitan Area can currently be observed (Table 5).

Another example is the town of *San Vicente*, where the first multi-family subdivision of the municipality was developed. Starting in 2005, its growth was notoriously exponential, consistent with the enormous migratory flow throughout the municipality (Table 5). The annexed subdivisions such as *La Misión* and *Infonavit San Vicente* have contributed enormously to their uncontrolled growth, allowing in turn irregular settlements such as the *Miramar* neighborhood, initially known as *cartolandia* – or paper board land- derived from the materials that the first settlers used to build their houses, and according to testimonials, estimates that 80% of the properties were invaded for “paratroopers or invaders”.

In Bahía de Banderas, the modifications to the environment are exposed in the reduction of deciduous forest, grassland, and other types of vegetation in the coastal zone and the deterioration from 1985 to 2011 is notorious, as well as the change in land use in the areas of *Punta de Mita* and *Nuevo Vallarta* (Zepeda, 2021).

As can be seen in Map 1, most of the territory is made up of deciduous and sub-deciduous forests, except for the strip with the highest concentration of tourist infrastructure, as well as the area for agricultural purposes. In general, the growth of the urban sprawl has grown rapidly in the *Las Juntas-El Zancudo* rural corridor in recent years, exerting strong pressure on local productive activities, as this flat strip is the one with the highest agricultural production (Fig. 2).

Thus, both single-family and multi-family subdivisions are built, among which we can mention *Los Cipreses*, *Real Ixtapa*, *La Primavera*, *Zenya*, *Ecoterra*, *Colinas del Valle*, *Campestre Los Ángeles*, *Verde Valle*, among others.

Thus, between the disproportionate growth of real estate-housing development and tourism megaprojects, changes in land use and changes in the landscape are exposed; some with riots due to social

discontent, such as the case of the *Corral del Risco* town in *Punta de Mita*, where one of the most visible disposessions of recent decades took place to make way for high-end tourism development (Zepeda & Costa, 2020).

Fig. 2 – Land use and vegetation AMIPV-BB
Source: Authors, 2022

Other megaprojects such as *Litibú*, *Punta Paraíso San Pancho*, and the most representative, *Vidanta* in Bahía de Banderas have also exerted strong pressure on the territory, with the towns of *Higuera Blanca*, *San Pancho*, and *Jarretaderas*, respectively, being the most affected (Zepeda and Coast 2020, 2021). In the southern zone of the Metropolitan Area, we find tourist complexes in the *Marina Vallarta*, *Conchas Chinas*, and *Amapas*, among the main ones.

Fig. 3 – Location of Infrastructure and Tourist Services, AMIPV-BB, 2022
Source: INEGI, 2022

It is thus observed that the infrastructure and tourist services constitute an urban sprawl along the coast, corresponding to a segregated development (Vera et al., 2013).

3.2 Social and cultural dimension

a. Conservation of cultural heritage

Historically, the entire region that today includes the AMIPV-BB was part of the State of Jalisco during the 19th century until its constitution in 1917 of the Free and Sovereign State of Nayarit, defining the current geographical delimitation. Thus, the region that is today a tourist region is politically and administratively divided.

Despite this division, a large part of the uses, customs, and lifestyles have formed a homogeneous society. However, the high migratory flows of the last decades have allowed an acceleration of the adoption of new cultural practices, as well as the emergence of the phenomenon of "deterritorialization", that is, the destruction of the territory and social constructions of identity based on the circumscribed space (Zepeda, 2021), even more, the rooting remains vulnerable, since it implies the lack of construction of a link between the inhabitant and the space they inhabit (Hiernaux & Lindón, 2004).

Hence, a study carried out with university students from the AMIPV-BB indicates that only half of them have heard about traditional dishes, such as "*cuala*", "*colado*" or "*gorditas de carne*", a more critical scenario is observed with the typical festivals or events such as the "*Fiesta del Rebozo*", which the new generations are practically unaware of (Zepeda et al., 2015). At the other extreme are the events that have had a mercantilist intervention around tourism, such as the *Fiestas de Mayo*, which 8 out of 10 young people say they know, and the "*Tuba*", known by almost all the interviewees.

However, the most illustrative opinion of deterritorialization is perhaps the opinion expressed regarding the "remodeling" -destruction - of historic public spaces that took place during the period 2004–2006, such as the case

of *Parque Hidalgo*, which during the first half of the 20th century, it served as a cemetery and housed a significant amount of the human bone remains from the first inhabitants of the municipality. In this regard, only 24% stated that they were against the destruction of heritage. In addition, practically 6 out of 10 young people do not know any story, myth, or legend of the region (Zepeda et al., 2015).

Equally important are the results of studies carried out by the University of North Carolina that reveal a forgotten archaeological zone in the municipality, located mainly in the *Ixtapa* area, whose main mound lost more than half of its volume due to having been used as a bank of material for the construction industry, so that it ended sliced up to more than half (Mountjoy, 1993, 1998), and whose other mounds are practically covered by urban sprawl.

On the other hand, in Bahía de Banderas the impacts of tourism on cultural changes are perceived as low. When asked the question "*How much does tourism affect your customs and lifestyles?*" to residents, 63% responded that the affectation is "little" or "nothing"; consequently, there may be no recognition of identity in terms of the loss of autochthonous lifestyles, such as the forms of coexistence and traditional tasks that the new generations do not perform when employed in tourism companies (Zepeda, 2021).

The agrarian nuclei have played a preponderant role in the de-agrarianizing, before the opening of capitals for the purchase of communal land in the Agrarian Reform of 1992, few *ejidos*⁵ remained outside of speculation. The case of *Ejido de Valle de Banderas*, one of the largest and oldest in the region, was refractory to urban massification until 2015 when the then President stated that

"[...] this town [Valle de Banderas] has remained traditionalist, because it is one of the towns that, despite being the municipal seat, continues to remain small, and to a certain extent we like it because we all still know each other [...] here we still

⁵ An *ejido* is an area of communal land used for agriculture in which community members have usufruct rights.

know with whom we talk to and we like, so much so that we have not allowed slums to be created, many developers have come to want to do subdivisions of social interest and we do not want to"- President Ejido Valle de Banderas in 2015 (Zepeda, 2021).

The previous expression refers to a certain resistance on the part of some sectors of the population, although insufficient in the face of the obvious *La Misión* real estate development, practically at the gates of the town of Valle de Banderas.

Agrarianizing leads to the abandonment of the family nature of the agricultural activity: agriculture is no longer a family activity, and the new generations migrate to the area with the greatest tourist economic dynamics, generating an effect of the relative decrease in its population, as can be seen in the Sierra localities, such is the case of Fortuna de Vallejo and Los Sauces (Zepeda, 2021).

b. Social well-being and perceived quality of life

The notion of social well-being has evolved from an idea directly associated with the levels of access to material goods to a multidimensional concept that includes material, psychological, and emotional well-being. Deaton (2015) in his work *The Great Escape*, generates the idea that well-being is all the things that make life good, that is, material well-being, reflected in income and wealth; physical and psychological well-being, with health and happiness; and education and the ability to participate in civil society through democracy and the rule of law.

In an approach to the tourism issue and from a Latin American perspective, Cordero

(2006) states that the degree of the well-being of a society is also given by the access to leisure and recreation, that is, the type of tourist recreation that is consumed.

One of the most widely used objective indicators is the level of poverty, which in itself is complex as it is made up of various dimensions because it is a multidimensional phenomenon by avoiding using only income as an approximation of economic well-being. In Mexico, one of the most unequal countries in the world, the National Council for the Evaluation of Social Development Policy (Coneval) takes into account *per capita income*, educational lag, access to health and social security services, as well as such as the quality and spaces of the home, access to food and the degree of social cohesion.

In this way, the value of the current basic food and the non-alimentary basket is a parameter that contributes to the estimation of poverty and vulnerability by income, which means that a person needs to reach a minimum monthly income to get out of the income line of poverty. In this sense, the last registered value of the food basket in urban areas reaches 44.32 pesos per person, while the food basket plus non-alimentary⁶ is 3,542.14 pesos (Coneval, 2022).

Therefore, CONEVAL establishes indicators based on two variables: economic well-being and social deprivation (deficiencies), hence the following groups or categories are generated: a) population in a situation of poverty, b) vulnerable population due to social deprivation, c) vulnerable population due to social deprivation and d) non-poor-non-vulnerable population⁷.

Table 8 shows the indicators for both

⁶ The basic food basket includes basic grains (corn, beans, etc.), meat, fish, eggs, milk and derived products, fruits, and vegetables. The non-food basket includes Transportation, Education, Culture, Recreation, Clothing, and footwear, among others (Coneval, 2022).

⁷ Multidimensional poverty: Population with income below the value of the income poverty line and suffering from at least one social deprivation. Vulnerable Population: Presents one or more social deprivations, but whose income is equal to or higher than the income poverty line. Vulnerable population by income: It does not present social deprivations and whose income is below the income poverty line. Non-poor and non-vulnerable population: a population whose income is equal to or higher than the poverty line by income and who does not have any social deprivation (Coneval, 2018).

municipalities, which shows the similarity and homogeneity of the society in terms of poverty and social vulnerability of the AMIPV-BB.

Table 6 – Multidimensional poverty indicators in AMIPV-BB, 2020

Indicator		Proportion (No. of people)	
		Municipality Puerto Vallarta	Bahía de Banderas
Poverty situation (extreme or moderate)		1 in 3	
Vulnerable due to	income	1 in 10	1 in 12
	social deprivation	1 in 5	2 out of 5
Not poor-Not vulnerable		1 in 4	

Source: Own elaboration based on information from Coneval, 2020

Additionally, according to previous studies by the Integral Tourism Observatory (2019) in which the basic basket was updated according to the National Consumer Price Index (INPC), in *Ixtapa*, 62.6% have some degree of poverty or vulnerability, in addition, it seems to concentrate the largest number of people in a situation of deprivation due to quality and housing spaces, which seems to coincide with the empirical evidence on possible social problems around the precariousness of housing and food since the local government delivers pantries monthly in *El Zancudo*, *El Ranchito* and the *Cantón* (DIF, 2019).

Given the complexity of the concept, indicators of various kinds have been developed to measure social well-being. To incorporate subjective aspects such as the perception of individuals and their social relationships, ECLAC issued in 2012 a proposal for subjective indicators that include satisfaction with life and happiness, social support, and empowerment, revealing their complexity in validity and reliability derived from memory biases and mood states (Villatoro, 2012).

In the same sense, the social perception of the resident population has become an extremely relevant variable for obtaining the "social license" that grants legitimacy to economic activity, in this case, tourism. According to the results of an investigation in 2018, the perception of the inhabitants of Puerto

Vallarta refers that tourism has brought with it an increase in problems of alcoholism, drug addiction, violence, and prostitution; as well as the destruction of green areas, water pollution and dirt on beaches and rivers. In addition, practically all respondents dedicated to the agricultural sector said that their economic situation has worsened in recent years (Virgen, 2018).

In contrast, 42 % of the surveyed population believed that tourism has helped a lot to reduce unemployment and increase the local economy and that there has been an improvement in the economic situation for those who are engaged in commerce in recent years (Virgen, 2018).

Consistent with the above, testimonies from people in communities affected by the tourist mega-developments in Bahía de Banderas point to changes in the use of land and landscape, as well as consistent pressure on their native lifestyle and productive activities, since practically the access to the beaches is limited (Zepeda and Costa, 2018).

"[...] that development, *Litibú*, we are talking about there being coconut oil palm trees, there were other types of trees that felling them did affect the environment, even though they planted another type of smaller palm, but there was a thick area that was demolished to make this development [...] since this place was settled, people dedicated themselves to fishing and that is how their life began to survive [...] people continue to go fishing but since there are more people there is less product" (Sic) (Municipal Delegate of Higuera Blanca 2002–2005; in Zepeda & Costa, 2018).

Contradictory, the notion of well-being is highly positive, since the social perception of tourism is satisfactory. According to a study conducted in 2018 on the resident population of Bahía de Banderas, it indicates that 84.1% of the population perceive tourism as beneficial, only 1.4% perceive it as negative and a high 9.4% have no idea about it (Zepeda, 2019).

On closer inspection, it is striking that

the negative perception is mainly concentrated in the social stratum that then earned between 10,000 and 15,000 pesos a month, that is, social strata substantially above the poverty threshold levels and, as expected, those in the lowest strata do not even pay attention to it because "they have not thought about it" (Zepeda, 2019:179).

Problems related to street cleaning, vacant lots, and bad odors are among the most recurrent in the perception of the population of Bahía de Banderas, with the town of *Mezcales* being the most sensitive, followed by *Jarretaderas* (Ibid., 2019). Due to their location next to the beach area, these towns coexist on the line of segregation, on the one hand, the opulence of a first-world infrastructure, framed by the tourist imagination, and, on the other, their reality within their communities.

A general aspect of the population of Bahía de Banderas is the idea of the inflationary effect generated by living in a tourist place. Thus, most of the interviewees indicated that tourism affected "very much" the cost of food and housing (Zepeda, 2019).

Regarding the future perspective, the statistical data showed a similar perception in all social strata. This aspect can be particularly useful since prospects are linked to the well-being of the individual (Omar, 2007). In this way, the population of Bahía de Banderas considers that "there is a good quality of life", "there is access to quality education", "there is a possibility to progress", and "there is an opportunity for my children" (Zepeda, 2019: 190).

3.3 Economic dimension

a. Occupation and lodging

The evident impact on the tourism sector due to the crisis caused by COVID-19 implied a setback in the progress due to the increase in the attraction of tourism in the world's tourist destinations. Faced with a controversial national open-door policy during the health crisis, Mexico managed to cushion the negative effects of sanitary restrictions. Puerto Vallarta and Nuevo Vallarta⁸ of the

AMIPV-BB remained during 2020, the year with the greatest impact due to the pandemic, at between 34% and 38% occupancy. The evolution of hotel occupancy from 2018 to May 2022 is shown in Table 7.

Table 7 – The average percentage of hotel occupancy AMIPV-BB 2018–2022

Year \ Destination	Puerto Vallarta	Nuevo Vallarta
2018	71.9	77.7
2019	72.4	77.3
2020	37.9	33.9
2021	56.4	48.4
2022 (as of Oct.)	71.3	64.6

Source: Datatur, 2022

A favorable aspect is homogeneity in the provision of services in the AMIPV-BB. According to Information from the Tourist Observatory (2018), the evaluation of lodging establishments is favorable in both markets regardless of the municipality where it is located, highlighting the price-quality and friendliness relationship.

While the offer of unregulated accommodation through the real estate sector is present in both markets, mainly in the national one, predominantly staying at the home of friends or relatives, rented houses / apartments, and own house (Observatorio Turístico, 2018).

According to the website of platforms such as Airbnb, in the municipality of Puerto Vallarta, there are an estimated 613 accommodation units, predominantly apartments, and rooms in shared accommodation. The prevailing prices are estimated at \$5,360 a night at home and \$1,100 a night in an apartment, in private rooms, most of them are around 600 pesos⁹ (IIEG, 2022).

b. Tourist profile and satisfaction

Market trends show that AMIPV-BB is a family destination: 62% of the national market claims to travel with family and to a lesser extent with friends (22.3%) and partners (12%) (Observatorio Turístico, 2018). This confirms that the AMIPV-BB is consolidated as a family

⁸ Nuevo Vallarta is the beach center of Bahía de Banderas monitored by the Ministry of Tourism (Datatur, 2022)

⁹ Prices in Mexican pesos per night without taxes.

destination in the national market primarily in summer and spring, coinciding with the two main reasons for travel: rest and visiting friends or family in the case of summer. In the winter period, the "weddings or romance" segment appears more clearly, positioning itself as one of the main reasons for visiting the region.

Likewise, based on the average income of visitors to the region, it is primarily the middle classes corresponding to socioeconomic levels¹⁰ C- and C. The estimate indicates that the high-end segment only reaches 3.5% market share in 2018.

The foreign market has its greatest presence in the region during the winter months from November to March, mainly with the so-called North American *snowbirds*. In particular, the Canadian tourist reaches a longer period of stay and, in general, the foreign tourist is located mainly in the middle classes and, to a lesser extent, upper classes.

Likewise, according to information from the Tourism Observatory (2018), the following assessments are made:

- a. The way of knowing the destination is similar in both markets: previous visits, Internet, and referrals (by word of mouth).
- b. Around 18% of the national market organizes its trip once it is in the destination, the foreigner does it at least two months in advance.
- c. In both markets, the least visited attractions are cultural attractions such as churches, as well as the mountains and inland towns, since they are limited to the tourist strip.
- d. National tourism is guided by activities such as local boat trips and SPA services.
- e. The positive perception of public safety at the destination is maintained.

Additionally, it is estimated that the percentage of visitors to the domestic market with some type of disability grew more than 5 percentage points from 2017 to 2018, going

from 2.58% to 7.89%.

At the same time, Puerto Vallarta is known internationally for being a *gay-friendly* destination. The LGBT+ segment is known worldwide for its spending capacity, which means a very important economic impact, mainly in the southern part of the city, better known as the "romantic zone", whose economic dynamics and nightlife is evident and verifiable through the indicators offered by the National Statistical Directory of Economic Units (2022), which corroborate that the number of food, retail and leisure establishments is higher than in any other point of the AMIPV-BB.

The LGBT+ segment is oriented towards caring for nature, in addition to the entertainment industry. 13.7% of those interviewed in this segment traveled with their pet in 2017, above the traditional family segment; In addition, 30.5% have a postgraduate degree, it is the segment with the highest academic level and income level, 51.8% obtain income greater than USD 90,000 per year, which in turn has contributed to the increase due to the demand for unregulated accommodation and second residence (Tourist Observatory, 2018).

For its part, the cruise segment spends much less than is usually thought. According to a survey of international cruise passengers carried out in January 2017 by the Integral Tourist Observatory, just over 50% of those interviewed mentioned having consumed food in local establishments, of which 80% said they spent less than \$40 on it. In general, 40% stated that they spent less than USD \$50 during their stay at the destination (Tourism Observatory, 2017), below the estimated USD \$62 in 2010 (Gauna et al., 2010).

3.4 Political-Institutional dimension

a. Territorial planning instruments.

As a priority aspect, there is the unresolved problem of metropolitanize. The first efforts were made at the federal level in 1977, when the conurbation Area of the *Cuenca del Rio Ameca* was declared a priority area, formulating the Regional Urban Development

¹⁰ Socioeconomic levels (SEL) in Mexico established by the Mexican Association of Market Intelligence Agencies. URL: www.amai.org.

Plan, which served as the basis for the subsequent General Law on Human Settlements in articles 11 and 16-b as well as in the state laws of Urban Development of Jalisco and Nayarit (Baños et al., 2015: 157)

It took several decades for new management instruments to be designed. In 2002, the Master Plan for Urban and Tourist Development was drawn up, the objective of which was to integrate a strategic vision to promote a management system that would promote the integral development of the area, but unfortunately, everything remained on paper since the main proposals were not implemented (Ibid.: 159).

Among the recent instruments of metropolitan management, the Inter-municipal Association Agreement stands out at the initiative of local governments and was approved by the state congresses in 2010, which allowed, among other things, access to extraordinary resources from the federal government. Only two years later, the formation of the Conurbation Commission of the Puerto Vallarta-Bahía de Banderas Interstate Metropolitan Zone was published in the Official Gazette of the Federation (DOF 09/14/2012) based on an agreement that includes commitments in terms of economic and tourism promotion, road infrastructure, mobility, and transportation, as well as drinking water and sanitation services. A quick diagnosis of the guidelines makes it possible to notice the discontinuity in the actions for the integration of the area, mainly in road and mobility aspects, as well as water and sanitation (Table 8).

Fortunately, an action that took place in April 2010 was the homologation of the Bahía de Banderas time zone with that of Puerto Vallarta, which represented a respite for the local population and businessmen in general. Bahía de Banderas used the Pacific Time zone, like the rest of Nayarit, contrary to Puerto Vallarta, which uses the center of the country, which caused a permanent problem of delays and general confusion. This situation ended when the time of the municipality of Bahía de Banderas was homologated to the time zone of Jalisco.

Table 8 – Diagnosis of AMIPV-BB strategic guidelines

Diagnosis	Strategic guidelines
Road infrastructure	The main connectivity is through the Ameca River Bridge, whose saturation generates social unrest derived from the vehicular load; The Federation Bridge project, in force for more than a decade, is expected to be completed during the current federal administration, it would unite both municipalities through the towns in the interior and requires the political will of both local governments. Through the agricultural area, there is a dirt road that serves as an alternative for the local population during the dry season
Mobility and transport	Public and private transport rates are differentiated (taxi and urban transport) and there is no coordination between service providers and carrier unions, due to the omission of government leadership, generating social unrest due to the lack of comprehensive inter-municipal routes. Regulation and control are different in both municipalities
Water and sanitation infrastructure	Each municipality supplies services without collegiate or collaborative work, even though the federal authority indicates that a conurbation water supply and treatment system must be established in the area, integrating the infrastructure elements

Source: Authors, 2022

In December 2019, the metropolitanize process finally began with the signing of an agreement to become the first interstate tourist metropolitan area in Mexico, under the commitment of both municipal and state governments before the Federal Secretariat of Territorial and Urban Development (SEDATU).

These efforts are significant steps, albeit insufficient. Empirical evidence shows, on the one hand, a gap in the homologation of laws and regulations that allow more homogeneous inter-municipal management for the benefit of the urban area. Both the private sector and civil society have put on the table the urgency of doing more work together, despite the political-administrative differences.

Discussion and conclusions

A tourist destination is a mental concept

(UNWTO, 2013), it cannot be defined in the strict sense of political-administrative divisions, the conjoint design of common objectives, as well as actions and shared responsibility, becomes the basis on which it must rest the tourist destination planning. Below are some of the challenges and opportunities identified for the AMIPV-BB (Table 9).

Table 9 – Challenges and Opportunities for the AMIPV-BB

<i>Challenges</i>	<i>Opportunities</i>
1. Environmental Protection	The intervention of the various sectors of society for the conservation of the Estero El Salado, as well as the care for the carrying capacity of the <i>Islas Marietas</i> National Park, the mountainous area, and District 10 in Puerto Vallarta will allow for maintaining the natural heritage for the benefit of the resident population and tourism
2. Organize urban and territorial growth	Avoid the collapse of drinking water supply and sanitation services and the reduction of a segregated tourism development model
3. Recovery of historical and cultural heritage	Generation of a sense of belonging and territoriality among the inhabitants. Work together with the <i>ejido</i> nuclei for the recovery and restoration of archeological identity elements and the construction of a museum <i>in situ</i> , contributing at the same time to the diversification of the tourist product
4. Reduce social debt	Accelerate road solutions and specify coordination between water utility agencies and intervene in the inflationary effect on housing. Reduce the percentage of the population (80%) that is below the levels of well-being or with at least one social deprivation. Lower the incidence of sexual exploitation associated with tourism
5. Diversification of the tourist product	Design and develop new tourism products based on the profile and the new megatrends in the

<i>Challenges</i>	<i>Opportunities</i>
	post-Covid era. There are elements to consider "Accessible Tourism" as an important opportunity in the short-medium term, as well as exploring innovative ideas for the LGBT+ segment and increasing spending by cruise passengers, diversifying leisure and food options during their stay in the city
6. To concretize the metropolitanized and the inter-state coordinated work	Access additional federal funds to benefit the metropolitan area as a whole. Generate synergy for the positioning of a strong tourism brand, avoiding contradictory approaches such as changing tourism brands without consulting key players in tourism development ¹¹

Source: Authors, 2022

The contrasts of development in mass tourist destinations have been repeatedly addressed from the broad perspective of Social Sciences since the 1970s (Jurdao, 1990). In the case of Mexico and, particularly, of the Puerto Vallarta area, the issue of disorderly growth is addressed in the studies of Nancy Evans in the eighties in the book "Tourism, Passport to Development?" coordinated by Emanuel De Kadt (1991) in which the initiative of the Executive Power to direct the economic activity of this area of the Mexican Pacific towards tourism is strongly suggested, as well as the socio-cultural effects in developing countries. In the Puerto Vallarta and Bahía de Banderas Metropolitan Area a replica of the extractivist capitalist model is identified that seems to accentuate inequality and socio-spatial segregation.

Tourism was one of the sectors most affected by the COVID-19 pandemic worldwide, the Organization world of Tourism esteem a loss of 120 million jobs around of world(WTO, 2020). Hence, the search for alternatives is imperative for both the recovery of jobs and the tourist demand. The remnants that are still preserved in the *Ixtapa-Las Palmas* corridor

¹¹ The Governor of the State of Nayarit recently decreed the change of the Nuevo Vallarta brand to "Nuevo Nayarit" without prior consultation and due to social and business discontent.

open up the possibilities for their use through responsible management, both for the reinforcement of identity values and the tourism sector, without losing the area's vocation, which would contribute to the local and regional development, at the same time as the recognition and revaluation of rural and archaeological heritage, even more so in Post-Covid tourism as it is oriented towards low-impact activities.

The development of tourism in the tourist region has been generated in a contradictory way, on the one hand, Puerto Vallarta is a tourist destination in a phase of stagnation (Butler, 1980) and Bahía de Banderas seeks its consolidation, even with the relaunch of its tourist brand, before the substantial change from Rivera Nayarit to Nuevo Nayarit. The

foregoing allows us to notice the urgency of joining efforts for coordinated work based on common objectives.

In short, the integral planning of the tourist destination could be the cornerstone on which to begin to build a new stage for the region, in which it is considered as one, beyond the political-administrative divisions, the metropolitan area is formalized for the benefit of the resident population, the offer of the tourist product is diversified considering the various micro-regions that comprise it and its potential within the framework of sustainability. Innovation and new technologies must be part of the plan, it is essential for its survival as a tourist destination in an increasingly competitive globalized world.

References

1. Aguilar, P. (2010). Bahía con horario central a partir del 4 de abril. *Noticiaspv.com*
2. AZ Noticias (2018). *Periódico en línea*. URL: <https://aznoticias.mx/index.php/puerto-vallarta-movil/30751-puerto-vallarta-es-el-tercer-destino-mas-demandado-en-el-mundo-en-airbnb-para-fin-de-ano>
3. Azcué Vigil, I. (2018). El desarrollo de la planificación estratégica del turismo en el marco de la participación de los actores y el contexto político local: análisis del caso del partido de Mar Chiquita (Argentina). *Revista Turydes: Turismo y Desarrollo*, 24.
4. Baños Francia, J. A., Tovar Ramírez, R., & Muñoz Viveros, M. (2015). Territorio, urbanismo y crisis en el espacio del turismo. Apuntes sobre la gestión metropolitana en la Bahía de Banderas. En: *Desarrollo, Crisis y Turismo*. México: Universidad de Guadalajara, 147-170.
5. Benidorm Communication (2019). *Página web oficial*. URL: <https://benidorm.org/comunicacion/en/article/benidorm-achieves-certification-worlds-first-smart-tourist-destination>
6. Butler, R. (1980). The Concept of Tourism Area Cycle of Evolution: Implications for Management of Resources. In: R. Butler (ed.). *The Tourism Life Cycle*, 1, Applications and Modifications.
7. Oliveira, M. C. B. d., & Pimentel, T. D. (2023). Turismo como solución espacial: el proceso de urbanización extensiva y concentrada del turismo en destinos de sol y playa de la periferia del capitalismo. *Ateliê Geográfico*, 16(3), 59–79. doi: 10.5216/ag.v16i3.71827.
8. Cavalcanti, P. (2006). *Um Olhar Crítico sobre o Conselho Nacional de Turismo: Articulação do Setor, Legitimidade e Auto-Interesse na Construção das Políticas Públicas*. s.l.: Escola de Administração de Empresas de São Paulo.
9. César Dachary, A. (2006). *De la Sociedad del Espectáculo a la Globalización*. México: Universidad de Guadalajara.
10. Comisión Europea de Turismo y Organización Mundial del Turismo (2013). Manual de desarrollo de productos turísticos. En: s.l.:OMT.
11. CONEVAL (2018). *Consejo Nacional de Evaluación de la Política de Desarrollo Social*. URL: <https://coneval.org.mx/Normateca/Documents/ANEXO-Lineamientos-DOF-2018.pdf>
12. Cordero Ulate, A. (2006). *Nuevos ejes de acumulación y naturaleza. El caso del turismo*. Buenos Aires: CLACSO.

13. Cordero, A. (2000). Turismo y Dinámicas Locales: el caso de Flores, el Petén, Guatemala.. En: *Encuentros inciertos: globalización y territorios locales en Centroamérica*. San José: FLACSO-Costa Rica, p. n.d.
14. Datatur (2022). *Secretaría de Turismo*. URL: <https://datatur.sectur.gob.mx/SitePages/Tableros.aspx>
15. Deaton, A. (2015). *El Gran Escape*. México: Fondo de Cultura Económica.
16. Dewailly, J. (2006). *Tourisme et géographie, entre pérégrinite et chaos?* Paris: L'Harmattan.
17. Anjos, F. A. D., Henz, A. P., & Calçada de Lamare Leite, F. (2009) Planificación y Políticas Turísticas. Perfeccionamiento del modelo sistémico de Porto Belo (SC), Brasil. *Estudios y Perspectivas en Turismo*, 18, 434–448.
18. De Kadt, E. (1991). *El turismo ¿pasaporte al desarrollo?* Madrid: Endymion.
19. Đurić, Z., & Topley, J. P. (2023). Managing Sustainability in Local Tourism Destinations at the Organisation Level: Environmental Aspects of Sustainable Business Practice in Hotels. In: Marko Koščak, Tony O'Rourke, *Ethical and Responsible Tourism: Managing Sustainability in Local Tourism Destinations*. Routledge, 142-156.
20. Enríquez, J. (2008). Segregación y fragmentación en las nuevas ciudades para el turismo. Caso Puerto Peñasco. *Topofilia: Revista de Arquitectura, Urbanismo y Ciencias Sociales*, n.d.
21. Frías, J. (2019). *Estero El Salado, el héroe amenazado por la contaminación y el crecimiento urbano*. URL: <https://contralinea.net/estero-el-salado-el-heroe-amenazado-por-la-contaminacion-y-el-crecimiento-urbano/>
22. Frías, J. (2021). *Fauna del estero El Salado, amenazada por desechos de cubrebocas*. URL: <https://jalisco.quadratin.com.mx/principal/fauna-del-estero-el-salado-amenazada-por-desechos-de-cubrebocas/>
23. Gauna, C., Virgen, C., & Velázquez, M. (2010). La percepción de los turistas de cruceros sobre la calidad de los servicios en Puerto Vallarta. En: *Impactos y dimensiones del Turismo*. Puerto Vallarta: Universidad de Guadalajara, 87-100.
24. Gobierno de Jalisco (2018). *Página Oficial*. URL: <https://sistemadif.jalisco.gob.mx/sitio2013/boletines/jalisco-modelo-nacional-para-el-turismo-accesible>
25. Gobierno de Jalisco (2019). URL: <https://www.jalisco.gob.mx/>
26. INEGI (2015). *Anuario Estadístico y Geográfico de Nayarit*. México: Instituto Nacional de Estadística y Geografía.
27. INEGI (2017). *Anuario Estadístico del Estado de Jalisco*. s.l.: INEGI.
28. INEGI (2017). *Anuario Estadístico y Geográfico de Nayarit*. México: Instituto Nacional de Estadística y Geografía.
29. Instituto de Información Estadística y Geográfica de Jalisco (2020). *IIEG*. URL: <https://iieg.gob.mx/ns/>
30. Instituto Nacional de Estadística y Geografía (2019). *Directorio Estadístico Nacional de Unidades Económicas*. URL: <https://inegi.org.mx/app/mapa/denue/>
31. Jurdao, F. (1990). *España en venta*. Madrid: Endymion.
32. López, M., & Godoi, C. (2014). *Procedimientos metodológicos encontrados no turismo tustentável*. s.l. Universidade Federal do Ceará.
33. Marín, G. (2009). Turismo, globalización y desarrollo local: Puerto Vallarta y los retos por venir. *Estudios Demográficos y Urbanos*, 24(1), 219-247.
34. Narváez, M. (2017). *Agencia Informativa Conacyt*. URL: <http://conacytprensa.mx/index.php/tecnologia/tic/17394-cozumel-primera-isla-inteligente-caribe>
35. Observatorio Integral de la Región Turística Puerto Vallarta-Bahía de Banderas (2016). *Estudio de Percepción Social en torno al Turismo 2016*. URL: <http://observatorioit.org/publicaciones/>
36. Observatorio Integral de la Región Turística Puerto Vallarta-Bahía de Banderas (2016). *Estudio de Perfil y Satisfacción del Turista Nacional 2016*. URL: <http://observatorioit.org/publicaciones/>
37. Observatorio Integral de la Región Turística Puerto Vallarta-Bahía de Banderas (2016). *Informe-Resumen Demanda Turística Jul-Dic 2016*. URL: <http://observatorioit.org/publicaciones/>

38. Observatorio Integral de la Región Turística Puerto Vallarta-Bahía de Banderas (2016). *Resultado General 2do. semestre 2016*. URL: <http://observatorioit.org/publicaciones/>
39. Observatorio Integral de la Región Turística Puerto Vallarta-Bahía de Banderas (2017). *Informe Segmento Cruceros en Puerto Vallarta 2017*. URL: <http://observatorioit.org/publicaciones/>
40. Observatorio Integral de la Región Turística Puerto Vallarta-Bahía de Banderas (2017). *Segmento LGBT en Puerto Vallarta 2017*. URL: <http://observatorioit.org/publicaciones/>
41. Observatorio Integral de la Región Turística Puerto Vallarta-Bahía de Banderas (2018). *Perfil y Satisfacción del Turista Primavera 2018*. URL: <http://observatorioit.org/publicaciones/>
42. Observatorio Integral de la Región Turística (2016). *Estudio de Perfil y Satisfacción del Turismo Extranjero 2016*. URL: <http://observatorioit.org/publicaciones/>
43. Omar, A. (2007). Las perspectivas de futuro y sus vinculaciones con el bienestar y la resiliencia en adolescentes. *Psicodebate. Psicología, Cultura y Sociedad*, 141-154.
44. Santos, E. (1999). *La actividad turística en la Costa Occidental de Huelva*. s.l.: Diputación Provincial de Huelva.
45. SEGITTUR (ND). *Destino Turístico Inteligente*. URL: <https://destinosinteligentes.es/destinos/tequila/>
46. UNWTO (2023). *UNWTO World Tourism Barometer and Statistical Annex*, Jan. 2023. URL: <https://e-unwto.org/doi/abs/10.18111/wtobarometereng.2023.21.1.1>
47. Velasco, M. (2016). Entre el poder y la racionalidad: gobierno del turismo, política turística, planificación turística y gestión pública del turismo. *Pasos, Revista de Turismo y Patrimonio Cultural*, 14(3), Sp. Iss., 577-594.
48. Vera, F., López, F., Marchena, M., & Antón, S. (2013). *Análisis Territorial del Turismo y Planificación de Destinos Turísticos*. Valencia: Tirant Humanidades.
49. Villatoro, P. (2012). *La medición del bienestar a través de indicadores subjetivos: Una revisión*. Santiago: CEPAL.
50. Virgen, C. (2018). Los objetivos del desarrollo sustentable desde la perspectiva de los habitantes de Puerto Vallarta. En: *El turismo frente a los objetivos del desarrollo sustentable*. Puerto Vallarta: Universidad de Guadalajara, 81-100.
51. Zepeda Hernández, S. L. (2019). *Desarrollo y Turismo en el municipio de Bahía de Banderas, Nayarit*. Puerto Vallarta (Jalisco): Universidad de Guadalajara.
52. Zepeda Hernández, S.L., Costa de Carvalho, F. C., & Ortega Palomo, G. (2023). Corporate Social Responsibility in times of the pandemic, a comparative study: Puerto Vallarta, Mexico, and Málaga, Spain. In: M. Koščak, & T. O'Rourke. *Ethical and Responsible Tourism: Managing Sustainability in Local Tourism Destinations*. Routledge, 387-403.
53. Zepeda Hernández, S. L. (2021). *Desarrollo y Turismo en Bahía de Banderas. La Transformación de un territorio 1990-2020*. Puerto Vallarta: Universidad de Guadalajara.
54. Zepeda Hernández, S. L., & Costa de Carvalho, F. C. (2017). El desarrollo turístico y la utopía de la sustentabilidad en Bahía de Banderas, Nayarit. *Anais Brasileiros de Estudos Turísticos ABET*, 7(3), 29-41. doi: 10.34019/2238-2925.2017.v7.3199.
55. Zepeda Hernández, S. L., Huízar, M., & Enciso, M. (2015). La crisis de identidad en Puerto Vallarta y su influencia en la promoción del destino. En: *Desarrollo, Crisis y Turismo*. Puerto Vallarta: Universidad de Guadalajara, 293-308.
56. Zepeda, S., & Costa, F. (2020). Social and environmental impacts of tourism mega projects in Mexico. In: *Ethical and Responsible Tourism*. New York: Routledge, 303-325.